

THE EFFECTS OF INTERNET IN THE YOUTH’S OUTLOOK

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Annotation. The article is intended to discuss prominent issues in the youth’s outlook which is related to internet.

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The Internet is the result of scientific and technological progress, a product of culture. Currently, it is very difficult to imagine our day without the internet. The role of the global network in the lives of young people in particular is growing. The Internet has greatly facilitated the interaction and exchange of information between people living in different parts of the world. According to statistics, the largest number of Internet users in the world are young people aged 21 to 30 years. Internet is a mass and fast media. Today, every major institution, enterprise and organization has its own WWW-page. Several thousand electronic versions of newspapers and magazines are connected to the Internet. Over the past decade, the number of users of the global network has increased tenfold. The very convenient and popular way to search, receive and transmit information through the network ensures that the number of users is growing. In 2007, the number of Internet users in our country (including mobile Internet users) was one million, and by the end of 2021 this figure will exceed twelve million. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired a meeting on January 27, 2020 to discuss measures to ensure youth employment and meaningful organization of leisure time. A video conference was held. One of the factors in ensuring the employment of young people is their specialization in the required profession. At the meeting, it was criticized that so far the unemployed population and vacancies have not been considered in harmony. And the issue of engaging

young people through the Internet, sitting at home for young people, was also discussed. The Internet is the world's largest source of cultural entertainment. All forms of art and major industries - games, music, cinema and theater - are available on the Internet. You can play a game with your partner who is somewhere else in the world. You can get information about the activities of your desired rock band. You can solve puzzles, read riddles. Every day, network users send hundreds of millions of electronic messages to each other. Here's to you, the miracle of the XXI century! For many, the Internet serves as a regular mail. There is no need to pay for television, newspapers, because the Internet has this opportunity. The Internet is a huge creative world. Through the network, you can introduce and create yourself to everyone with the help of your personal home page. In short, the Internet, like all sciences, has become important for everyone. Just as there are two sides to the right coin, there are pros and cons to everything. In the vernacular, the Internet is a spider's web. In my opinion, a social network is like a sea. In it, both swimming and drowning depend on us. But today's development of the internet has led to a dramatic increase in the scale of ideological influence on young people. The role of the religious factor in conquering hearts using this means of development is high. That is why various religious extremist and terrorist groups are using the Internet as the most effective tool to promote their ideas. At the same time, the main task of religious extremist movements is to use modern information communications to achieve their goals, to propagate in different languages via the Internet and to create virtual communities on the basis of carefully designed rehab. For example, today, several major terrorist organizations are actively recruiting to their ranks, mainly people aged 17-35, through social networks. In order to further increase the effectiveness of the psychological impact, it carefully studies the pages of members of the social network, photos, comments and conversations, as well as the topics of conversation, and on this basis, It is sent through social networks with a wide audience, such as Telegram, Twitter, Whats App (text message, text, photos, stickers, audio-video clips) and interaction is established. the growing popularity of

them and the issuance of various kinds of destructive fatwas in them show how serious the problem is. Because the majority of the world's population is young. Young people are a great force. They are now formed whatever is imprinted on the coming mind is sealed like a pattern engraved on that stone. That is why such wonderful currents in the virtual world are trying to trap young people. Their confidence, energy and enthusiasm help them to achieve their goals. Unfortunately, such hateful forces are mainly far from science and enlightenment, trying to attract people who do not know the true meaning of pure religious concepts, especially young people, through social networks. Trying to leave their homeland by misinterpreting the concepts of ‘jihad’, ‘takfir’, ‘martyrdom’, ‘migration’. It is also widely used by some people to deliberately contradict the essence of Islam, to spread various baseless information, religious messages of unknown origin, or to intimidate people with photos and videos. At the same time, the fact that some young people believe in unsubstantiated information and data that contradicts our national and religious values, the source of which is not specified, and blindly accept it without thinking, has even more serious consequences. produces. As information has become a commodity today, everyone must cultivate a culture of consuming it. Is it only among the youth of Uzbekistan? Let's look at foreign countries to find out. Let us now turn our attention to Japan, which is called the "land of the rising sun." Japan is a very fast-growing country, which is mainly due to the Japanese nature of hard work and entrepreneurship. Striving for all the innovations and developments in the world, taking advantage of the latest achievements and further developing them - this has become an age-old national custom of the Japanese people. Today, Japan is open to all countries in the world and actively participates in the field of international cooperation. Life expectancy is an important indicator of a nation's health and quality of life. For the Japanese, family is the main source of livelihood. Divorce is much less common here than in other developed countries of the world. The Japanese education system is also unique. Preschool education usually begins with the family. For Japanese women, motherhood comes first. Many Japanese women

say that raising children is the goal of their lives. One of the main features of Japanese upbringing is that Japanese educators teach children to "han" in small groups. It teaches children to make decisions, respect the opinions of others, and make group members all proactive. In Japan, mother and child are very close. This closeness is also reflected in everyday life: mother and child sleep together, the mother carries the child for a long time. Find many notes in the Japanese fiction about sleeping together and carrying a baby possible. The mother-child relationship is reflected on an emotional level: the mother accepts everything the child does with love, patience, and care. European mothers, on the other hand, chose a different tactic: they explained to the children in detail how to assemble the pyramid. He then invited the children to do the work. Apparently, while Japanese mothers gave the concept of "do as I do," Western mothers only explained the theory and forced the children to do it all on their own. That is why Japanese education and upbringing is called "shy". Japanese mothers rarely force their children to do things they have never done before. They first set an example and make the child want to do the same. Before teaching a child to live in a community, it is important to explain what it means to see and respect the feelings and interests of those around you. That's why Japanese women, in turn, respect the sensitivity of children. They do not put too much pressure on children, do not embarrass them, but arouse the feelings of children. For example, if a child breaks a car, a Japanese mother will say, "The car is dying, she's crying now." "Don't do that, it's not good. How much work does it take to buy a car?" But so are our mothers. Perhaps we, too, would have been able to fully control ourselves when we were treated in the tactics of the Japanese from a young age. We could defend against any evil forces. The Japanese themselves do not prove that their methods are the only correct method. In recent times, western values have had a major impact on their traditions. However, the main principle of the Japanese approach is to treat children calmly, patiently and with full compassion. Since 2011, Tashkent Islamic University has introduced a special course "Information Consumption Culture" in all areas of undergraduate and graduate

programs. Information Consumption Culture, in the broadest sense, means a system of knowledge, abilities and skills that serve to receive, sort, understand and interpret information that serves the interests, maturity and development of society. In the younger generation, these aspects were formed to such an extent that the idea of decision is recognized by all today. . Therefore, to form the skills of today's youth to use the opportunities of the information world wisely. Therefore, the socio-political processes taking place in different regions of the world, the deepening of the sense of conflict, the organization of spiritual and educational work against all kinds of threats in accordance with modern requirements. In this regard, we must mobilize all our forces and capabilities to protect the young generation, which is our future, in short, our family, which is sacred to each of us, from the influence of foreign ideas under the guise of religion. it is necessary to acquaint them with the achievements of technology, but taking into account the negative consequences, it is expedient to inculcate in them the constant monitoring and explanatory work. Creating a healthy immunity in young people on the use of information flow, along with teaching the positive aspects, should also mention the negative consequences. Based on the results of the study, it is possible to draw such conclusions. The Internet today is a global computer network that covers almost the entire world. Internet communication is especially important for people whose real life is interpersonal poor for one reason or another. Such people use the Internet as an alternative to a direct (real) environment. Communication via the Internet does not have to be in only one country. Because the Internet is the Internet all over the world, people from different countries can communicate. Covering almost all the cultural corners of the planet, the World Wide Web is a powerful means of intercultural communication that promotes the rapprochement of peoples and the growth of national and international characteristics. I am convinced that the Internet has changed our lives for the better. It has only one drawback: some people become addicted to it and spend all day networking, online dating, or playing games. Overuse of the network can be dangerous because new technology victims ignore their families, friends,

jobs, and real hobbies. The internet is a wonderful thing! I am happy to live with it in the 21st century with modern technology and devices.